

Recovering from the COVID-19 pandemic in primary education: The overlooked role of non-cognitive skills

van Vugt, L.¹, Haelermans, C.^{1,3,4}, Olla, J.², Smeets, C.¹, & Schils, T.²

1. Research Centre for Education and the Labour Market (ROA), University of Maastricht, Maastricht, The Netherlands
2. Department of Macro, International and Labour Economics, University of Maastricht, Maastricht, The Netherlands
3. Netherlands Initiative for Education Research (NRO), The Hague, The Netherlands
4. National Education Lab AI (NOLAI), Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Summary

1. This study compares trends in cognitive skills (math, spelling, and reading) and non-cognitive skills (problem-solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness) before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. It combines test score data from the student tracking system used in the Netherlands Cohort Study on Education with data on non-cognitive skills from the OnderwijsMonitor Limburg.
3. Among Dutch primary school students in Limburg, the sharpest decline is seen in math. However, strong significant declines are also found in problem-solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness.
4. These findings underscore the urgent need to also include the non-cognitive skills as a key focus in the educational recovery agenda.

1. Introduction

After the first COVID-19 lockdown in the Netherlands, which was characterized by widespread school closures and a rapid shift

to remote learning, teachers focused their efforts primarily on core subjects such as math, spelling, and reading. This focus on foundational cognitive skills was seen in many countries, and accordingly, most of the existing international literature has

concentrated on the pandemic's impact on these subjects, offering valuable insights into learning losses.

However, less is known about how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the development of broader non-cognitive skills such as problem-solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness. Next to the core cognitive skills, these skills are essential for pupils to be well-prepared for the transition to secondary education and for success later in life (Akgum & Ciarrochi, 2003; Banawi et al., 2004; Dison et al., 2019; OECD, 2020; Shah et al., 2018).

In this policy brief, we compare trends in cognitive skills (math, spelling, and reading) with the development of broader non-cognitive skills (problem-solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness) before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Our analyses focus on a critical stage in children's educational pathways: the final two years of primary school, when students prepare for and transition into secondary education.

2. Data

Our analyses cover about 5,000 Dutch primary school students from Limburg. The data is collected every two years, allowing us to follow three cohorts over time. We compare their cognitive skills in 5th grade (aged 10–11) with their non-cognitive skills one school year later, in 6th grade (aged 11–12). In the Netherlands, these are the final two years of primary school, just before students' transition to secondary education.

To measure skills in math, spelling, and reading, we use data from the student tracking system (in Dutch: leerlingvolg-

systeem, LVS), as collected by the Netherlands Cohort Study on Education (Nationaal Cohortonderzoek Onderwijs, NCO)¹ (Haelermans et al., 2020). We used the results from the end-of-year test in grade 5 and standardized the scores of students from the school years 2019/2020 and 2021/2022 (i.e., during/post-COVID-19) against those from the school year 2017/2018 (pre-COVID-19).

To measure the non-cognitive skills of problem solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness, we use data from the Education Monitor Limburg (Onderwijs-Monitor Limburg, OML)². 6th-grade students (from the same cohorts as used in grade 5) were asked to respond to various statements in the student survey. These statements, used to measure the skills, are derived from established instruments developed by Stubbe et al. (2015) and Thijs et al. (2014), ensuring reliability and validity. After conducting a factor analysis, the following non-cognitive skills were constructed:

- Problem Solving: measured using the following statements "If I encounter a problem, I think of a plan to solve it" and "When I decide something, I have good reasons for this decision" (Cronbach's alpha = 0.7).
- Curiosity: measured with the following statements "I wonder how something is discovered", "I want to know how something works" and "I think it is interesting to think about things around me" (Cronbach's alpha = 0.7).
- Resourcefulness: measured with the following statements "I think of different ways to do an assignment", "I always have a lot of ideas when I get an assignment" and "I think of new things" (Cronbach's alpha = 0.7).

¹ Link to website (in Dutch only): www.nationaalcohortonderzoek.nl

² Link to website (in Dutch only): www.onderwijsmonitorlimburg.nl

We standardized the scores of the scales from the school years 2020/2021 and 2022/2023 (i.e., during/post-COVID-19) against those from the school year 2018/2019 (pre-COVID-19).

3. Results

Figure 1 shows the results of the standardized test scores from the end-of-year test for 5th grade students. Among the tested skills, spelling showed the smallest decline in test scores, both during and post-COVID-19, while math exhibited the largest drop compared to pre-COVID-19 levels.

Although spelling and reading scores showed some recovery since the start of COVID-19 until 2021/2022, reading still has test scores far below pre-COVID levels. In addition, the gap in maths scores even became slightly larger between 2019/2020 and 2021/2022 compared to pre-COVID-19, indicating a worsening trend in math performance over time.^{3 4}

Figure 1. Scores on end-of-year test grade 5 (standardized on pre-COVID-19 year)

Figure 2 shows the results of the three non-cognitive skills: problem solving, curiosity and resourcefulness for 6th grade students. Problem solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness all declined compared to pre-

COVID-19 levels and showed barely or no signs of recovery between 2020/2021 and 2022/2023. Notably, curiosity showed the largest decline.

Figure 2. Scores on non-cognitive skills grade 6 (standardized on pre-COVID-19 year)

When comparing these results with the results of 9th grade students in secondary education (not shown here), we observe a decline in problem-solving between 2017/2018 and 2021/2022 (van Vugt et al., 2023b). Curiosity remains stable over this period, while resourcefulness shows an increase (van Vugt et al., 2023a).

If we compare Figure 1 and Figure 2, math shows the most significant decline. Not only lower than the scores for spelling and reading, but also lower than the declines observed in problem solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness. However, national data indicate an upward trend in the core subjects such as math and reading after 2021/2022, especially when looking at national numbers for the Netherlands (Van Vugt et al., 2024), so this decline may turn around for our sample in the next years as well. In contrast, worrying developments for non-cognitive skills persist at the national level, both in primary as well as in secondary education.

³ However, this worsening trend for Math does not seem to continue in school year 2023/2024.

⁴ In general, the declines in scores are less pronounced in the Netherlands as a whole compared to the Limburg region.

The combination of setbacks in both cognitive and non-cognitive skills, as measured in this policy brief, raises concerns about increased risks of academic underperformance, grade repetition, and early school leaving. These challenges could, in turn, lead to problematic school-to-work transitions and a potential rise in the number of NEETs (youth not in education, employment, or training).

4. Conclusion

While during and after the COVID-19 pandemic much attention has rightfully been given to recovering cognitive skills such as math, spelling, and reading, this policy brief shows that non-cognitive skills have also largely declined compared to pre-COVID-19 times. Yet these skills, including problem-solving, curiosity, and resourcefulness, are just as essential for students' long-term success in education and beyond as the cognitive skills.

Now is the time to act. Policymakers have already devoted significant attention to recovering learning losses in math, spelling, and reading. However, if we fail to also address the gaps in non-cognitive skills development, we risk disadvantaging the generation of students who grew up during the COVID-19 pandemic, not only in their schooling, but also in their future participation in society and the labour market. Strengthening non-cognitive skills must therefore become a central part of the educational recovery agenda.

What is BRIDGE?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

References

- Akgun, S., & Ciarrochi, J. (2003). Learned Resourcefulness Moderates the Relationship Between Academic Stress and Academic Performance. *Educational Psychology*, 23(3), 287–294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144341032000060129>
- Banawi, A., Rumasoreng, M., Hasanah, N., Rahawarin, D., & Basta, I. (2024). The Relationship between Problem-Solving Skills and Student Academic Achievement: A Meta-Analysis in Education. *Journal of Ecohumanism* 3(3):1287-1299. <https://doi.org/10.62754/joe.v3i3.3413>
- Dison, L., Shalem, Y. & Langsford, D. (2019). Resourcefulness matters: Student patterns for coping with structural and academic challenges. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 33(4): 76-93. <https://doi.org/10.20853/33-4-2831>
- Haelermans, C., Huijgen, T., Jacobs, M., Levels, M., van der Velden, R., van Vugt, L., van Wetten, S. (2020). Using data to advance educational research, policy, and practice: Design, content, and research potential of the Netherlands Cohort Study on Education. *European Sociological Review*, 36(4), 643–62. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcaa027>

- OECD. (2020). *Early Learning and Child Well-being - A Study of Five-year-Olds in England, Estonia, and the United States*. Paris: OECD.
<https://doi.org/10.1787/3990407f-en>
- Shah, P.E., Weeks, H.M., Richards, B., & Kaciroti, N., (2018). Early childhood curiosity and kindergarten reading and math academic achievement. *Pediatric Research*, 84, 380–386.
- Stubbe, H. E., Jetten, A. M., Paradies, G. L., & Veldhuis, G. J. (2015). *Creatief vermogen: de ontwikkeling van een meetinstrument voor leerlingen op school*. Soesterberg: TNO.
- Thijs, A., Fisser, P., & Van der Hoeven, M. (2014). *21e eeuwse vaardigheden in het curriculum van het funderend onderwijs*. Enschede: SLO.
- van Vugt, L., Haelermans, C., Abbink, H., Baumann, S., Hendrikse, A., Ronda, S. & Van Wetten, S. (2024). *Vier jaar sinds COVID-19: herstel ingezet voor begrijpend lezen en rekenen-wiskunde*. NCO Factsheet No. 2024-1.
https://www.nationaalcohortonderzoek.nl/sites/nco/files/media-files/factsheet_2024-1_npo_algemeen_v20241118_digit.pdf
- van Vugt, L., Ronda, V., & Schils, T. (2023a). *Niet-cognitieve vaardigheden middelbare scholieren: Vindingrijkheid en nieuwsgierigheid*. Maastricht University. OML factsheets No. 2023-003.
<https://onderwijsmonitorlimburg.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/FS2023-003-vo-nieuwsgierigheid.pdf>
- van Vugt, L., Ronda, V., & Schils, T. (2023b). *Niet-cognitieve vaardigheden middelbare scholieren: kritisch denken en probleemoplossend vermogen*. Maastricht University. OML factsheets No. 2023-004.
<https://onderwijsmonitorlimburg.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/2023-004-vo-kritisch-denken.pdf>

Funded by the European Union

BRIDGE is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101177154). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Follow us online www.bridge-horizoneurope.eu

Follow us on Bluesky [@bridgeproject.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/bridgeproject.bsky.social)

Follow us on LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/bridge-horizon-europe-project